

ISic3351

Honorific inscription for Marcus son of Publius

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object

block

Editor

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Autopsy

2011-06-15

Last Change

2019-04-01 - Jonathan Prag edited the file on the basis of autopsy and 2017 edition

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Found in 1971 in re-use in a dry-stone wall above the south corner of the west portico of the agora

Coordinates

37.997553, 14.262346

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory ME 20222

Physical Description

A grey limestone block, damaged to varying degrees on three sides. The left margin is intact; the upper edge is lightly damaged; the right margin is lost, extensively so across the lower right corner; the lower margin may be intact at the lower left corner, but is partially abraded. The surviving part of the inscribed face is damaged across the top margin (line 1), across the upper right corner (lines 1-3), and along the bottom margin (line 6), although showing some wear; the lower right portion is lost.

Dimensions

Height 31 cm

Width 37 cm

Depth 11-12 cm

Layout

The left side of six lines of Greek text are preserved.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are neatly cut, with light serifs. Omicron is full size; pi has equal, full-length hastae; mu has vertical outer hastae, but curving middle hastae, which do not always reach to the line; the central bar of the epsilon is detached from the vertical and shorter than the other two.

Letter heights:

Lines 1-6: 25-35 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. ὁ δᾶμος [τῶν Ἀλαισίνων]

2. Μάρκον []
3. Ποπλίου υἱὸν []
4. εὐνοίας ἔ[νεκεν καὶ]
5. εὐεργε[σίας τᾶς]
6. ἔς α[ύτων]

Apparatus

Text based on autopsy

Prestianni 2012: [Αἰμί]λι[ον?]

Prestianni 2012: ι[---]

Translation (en)

The people of the Halaesini (honour) Marcus [-?-] son of Publius [-?-], on account of his goodwill and beneficence towards them

Translation (it)

Il popolo degli Alesini (onora) Marcus [-?-] figlio di Publio [-?-], per la benevolenza e munificenza nei loro confronti

Commentary

Lines 1, and 4-6 can all be restored with confidence on the parallel of other similar honorific inscriptions from Halaesa (compare nos. 1, 2, 4, 5, 7 and the bronze of Nemenios no.59). These restorations in turn suggest a maximum width of 17 letters in line 1, and approximately 14-16 in lines 2 and 3. In line 2 this means up to 10 letters are lost, containing the nomen of Marcus, and in line 3 up to 5 letters, containing his cognomen, or just possibly tribus (the trace of a vertical stroke is visible after the final nu, compatible with either I or K). The nomen in line 2 has previously been restored as Αἰμίλιον, but the traces on the stone are incompatible with this: the first visible letter, which is either the third or the fourth of the name, could be be A or Λ, but it cannot be M; the second appears to be either M or N, but not I. Both Flaminius and Caninius are possible (both attested on the island in the Republican period), but the possibilities are multiple, and no identification is possible. Although Marcus is clearly a Roman citizen (and at least a second generation Roman, since he is son of Publius), he is probably not being honoured for actions as a Roman official, since there is no room in this text for the title which this would require (the closest parallel therefore is ISic0770 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0770>] for Marcus Aemilius Rho[--], a first generation Roman citizen, rather than ISic1178 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1178>] for C. Vergilius Balbus, a proquaestor).

Digital identifiers:

TM 645594

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Photo J.Prag